

**D5.1 Report on the
Stakeholders contact list and
the Communication procedure
established with stakeholders**

**WP5 Science to policy
translation to stakeholders**

Responsible Partner: BfR

Contributing partners: SSI, PMT members

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Starting Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	D5.1 Report on the Stakeholders contact list and the Communication procedure established with stakeholders
WP and Task	WP5; Task 5.1
Leader	Annemarie Käsbohrer, BfR
Other contributors	Kåre Mølbak, SSI, Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, the One Health EJP Project Management Team members
Due month of the deliverable	M2
Actual submission month	M2
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

Contents

1. Summary	4
2. Introduction	5
3. Stakeholders contact list	9
3.1. Process to establish and maintain the Stakeholders contact list	9
3.2. Stakeholders contact list, February 2018	13
4. Communication procedure with stakeholders	17
4.1. Process to establish the Communication procedure	17
4.2. Communication procedure with stakeholders, February 2018	18
5. List of abbreviations	19

1. Summary

Open and transparent dialogue between One Health EJP and stakeholders is needed to ensure that the One Health EJP absorbs the research and integrative needs of the stakeholders as well as to ensure the best use of the outcomes of One Health EJP by the stakeholders. This report describes the process to establish communication links with the stakeholders and the communication procedure with stakeholders. The communication has started actively, already before the official start of the One Health EJP in January 2018.

2. Introduction

The overall objective of the European Joint Programme (EJP) One Health (Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards) is to develop a European network of research institutes, mainly with reference laboratory functions. The EJP will integrate medical, veterinary, and food scientists in the field of food and feed safety in order to improve research on the prevention and control of mainly foodborne zoonoses, whilst taking into account the public health concerns of consumers and other stakeholders throughout the food chain. Following a One Health approach the EJP aims to create a sustainable European One Health framework by integration and alignment of medical, veterinary, and food institutes through joint programming of research agendas **matching the needs of European and national policy makers and stakeholders.**

One of the specific objectives of One Health EJP is to **exchange and communicate with all national and international stakeholders, and in particular the European Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (ECDC) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).** Stakeholder liaison actions include developing and maintaining contact with EFSA and ECDC to ensure that the overall objectives of the One Health EJP consortium are in accordance with the overarching policies of the respective agencies in relation to foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance, and emerging threats. The Stakeholders Committee supports the One Health EJP to identify synergies, avoid redundancy, ensure that the One Health EJP is aware of the research and integrative needs, and ensure that the stakeholders are aware and can consider the One Health EJP research results in their policies. ECDC and EFSA are among the stakeholders included in the Stakeholders Committee from the very beginning of One Health EJP.

The One Health EJP is structured into seven work packages (WP) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structure of One Health EJP. Work package 5 (WP5) focuses on science-to-policy translation to stakeholders, which are shown in the bottom of the figure.

Work package 5 (WP5) of One Health EJP is entitled ‘Science to policy translation to stakeholders’ and it is active during the whole length of One Health EJP (2018–2022, 60 months). The Lead Beneficiary is Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) and the Deputy Lead Beneficiary is Statens Serum Institut (SSI). The purpose of WP5 is to establish **a dialogue with EFSA and ECDC as well as EU policy makers as major stakeholders of the One Health EJP and also with other relevant international policy makers (WHO, OIE, FAO) and national stakeholders (national ministries and the mirror groups, if these are established)**. The needs identified by the risk-assessors will be taken into account in the procedure for updating strategic priorities defined in WP2. WP5 will also function as a channel for the One Health EJP to disseminate new scientific data to these stakeholders. WP5 reports to Stakeholders Committee, and takes into account the recommendations and feedback from the Stakeholders Committee.

The objectives of WP5 are:

- To develop procedures for an efficient information flow and interaction between science and European stakeholders (EU policy makers and EU agencies)
- To advocate for the One Health EJP and the One Health approach among EU policy makers (EC) and EU agencies (ECDC and EFSA)
- To communicate to the One Health EJP governing structure the research and integrative needs identified in policy processes of the European Commission and need for knowledge identified by the EU agencies (ECDC and EFSA)
- Vice-versa, to highlight how and when data resulting from activities within the One Health EJP could be used to improve policy initiatives, including risk management practices that addresses the protection of consumers health
- To support alignment of the scientific capacity within the consortium with other similar activities in EC member states in collaboration with WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP6.
- Together with WP1, communicate the scientific evidence based data to the EU stakeholders, the international stakeholders (WHO, OIE, FAO) and within the Member States

A Stakeholders contact list and a Communication procedure with the stakeholders are needed to:

1. ensure the research and integrative needs of the stakeholders are efficiently received by One Health EJP
2. ensure quick and efficient, tailored dissemination of results of One Health EJP to the stakeholders, and
3. allow timely alignment of One Health EJP activities with other activities.

Identification of the stakeholders and establishment of communication links is conducted by WP5 in collaboration with WP1 and WP2, to ensure that processes where project-based activities are subject to decision making will be aligned across the One Health EJP.

There is a close collaboration between WP5 and the Stakeholders Committee, which supervises the work of WP5. WP5 reports to Stakeholders Committee, and takes into account the recommendations and feedback from the Stakeholders Committee.

This report describes the process to establish communication links with the stakeholders and the communication procedure with stakeholders, and reports on the status of this process in February 2018.

3. Stakeholders contact list

3.1. Process to establish and maintain the Stakeholders contact list

3.1.1. Identification of stakeholders

Several Key stakeholders were identified already in the preparatory phase of One Health EJP. The three that have been decided to be included in the Stakeholders Committee from the first year of One Health EJP are ECDC, EFSA, and WHO (Europe), while including OIE was postponed. ECDC and EFSA are in the Stakeholders Committee from the very beginning of One Health EJP.

It should be noted that the Stakeholders Committee includes coordinators of EU-projects, in the beginning of One Health EJP those of COMPARE, EFFORT, and JPI AMR. The communication channel with them is through WP2.

First, these and other pre-identified stakeholders are extracted from the Annex 1 sections 1-3 and section 7 of the proposal, the Stakeholders Committee mandate, and from discussions with EC Representatives during the preparatory stage of the proposal.

The list of stakeholders is thereafter expanded and updated using the snowball approach. This also includes the expansion of the Stakeholders Committee. More stakeholders as well as different groups within the stakeholder organisations are actively searched for and identified during the activities of WP5, in particular the activities related to identifying research and integrative needs of the stakeholders, because the research focus is multidisciplinary. The identified stakeholders, members of the Stakeholders Committee, and the whole One Health EJP consortium are also engaged in identifying stakeholders. Moreover, stakeholders are provided possibilities to contact One Health EJP, e.g. via the website of One Health EJP. These procedures will be further developed in the future in close collaboration with the stakeholders.

In addition to simple listing of the stakeholders, relevant links between the stakeholders are identified. This is important for alignment and for targeted dissemination of output of One Health EJP.

Stakeholder categories

The stakeholders are divided into international and national stakeholders. The international stakeholders are divided into EU stakeholders, global stakeholders, and regional stakeholders. The national stakeholders are those of national or narrower scope.

- International stakeholders
 - EU stakeholders (especially ECDC and EFSA)
 - Global stakeholders (especially WHO, FAO, OIE)
 - Regional stakeholders
- National stakeholders (e.g. ministries)

The stakeholders with a clear link to One Health EJP activities at a level relevant for One Health EJP objectives are identified as Key stakeholders. The members of the Stakeholders Committee are always directly considered Key stakeholders.

Focus of One Health EJP is on EU-level, and thus the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA are the main focus for most activities of WP5. Of the national stakeholders, programme owners, other ministries, and mirror groups are implicitly also Key stakeholders.

The dialogue about research and integrative needs focuses on the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA that are also represented in the Stakeholders Committee. The dissemination activities of WP5 are also highly focused on the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA, but cover other identified stakeholders as appropriate.

Collaboration with stakeholders is not restricted to those represented in the Stakeholders Committee. For example, EC directorates are not directly involved in the work of WP5, but Directorate-General Health and Food Safety, European Commission, which is addressing risk assessment questions to EFSA and ECDC and which is mainly responsible for risk management decisions will be included in the discussions on research and integrative priorities and the communication of outcomes.

3.1.2. Establishing communication links with the stakeholders

First contacts and kick-off

The open dialogue with the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA was started by invitations to the Stakeholder Committee. At the Kick-off meeting (KOM) of One Health EJP in Paris 30.–31.1.2018, the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA presented their expectations, and One Health EJP introduced its structure. Moreover, European Commission was represented, by Directorate-General Agriculture and Rural Development, Directorate-General Health and Food Safety, and Department 'Industrial Leadership and Societal Challenges', Research Executive Agency, in the round table discussion at KOM. The dialogue was already very active.

The two representatives of the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA at the Stakeholders Committee, Piotr Kramarz and Marta Hugas, are the first Key contact persons. The contact at Directorate-General Health and Food Safety, European Commission, is Kris de Smet.

Structure analysis of international stakeholders to identify contact persons

To ensure that the dialogue and dissemination will be targeted efficiently, the internal structures of the international stakeholders are analysed from available online documents, presentations at KOM, and the dialogue with the first Key contact persons. The objective is to identify groups or persons within their own organisations and others, who are responsible for:

1. Strategy
2. Policy
3. Operational work and training

related to:

1. Foodborne zoonoses
2. Antimicrobial resistance
3. Emerging threats

These groups and persons are contacted by WP5 and asked to nominate contact persons for future correspondence.

To ensure no delay in establishing the Key communication links, this approach is first applied to the Key EU stakeholders, followed by other EU stakeholders, Key global stakeholders, and Key national stakeholders. The approach may be applied also for other global, regional, and national stakeholders.

Snowball approach to identify contact persons for national and regional stakeholders

National stakeholders (including programme owners, other ministries, and mirror groups in the individual Member States) are identified from the preparatory work (e.g. the contact lists compiled) and through the existing EFSA and ECDC Focal Points and the beneficiaries of One Health EJP. Procedures established by WP1 (Communication Groups, website) will contribute to identification of further contacts.

3.1.3. Maintaining and updating the Stakeholders contact list

The two Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA are mentioned on the public One Health EJP website. In addition, there will be instructions for how to contact the One Health EJP via the website.

The Stakeholders contact list will be expanded during the One Health EJP, and include more Key stakeholders and other stakeholders, as they are being identified.

The Stakeholders contact list will be built on two levels: the higher level is the main contact person representing each stakeholder, and the second level are the persons representing specific groups within the organisation of the stakeholder. This is to ensure efficient information flow and targeted dissemination.

The Stakeholders contact list is maintained and updated regularly by WP5. The first Stakeholders contact list is compiled by the end of February 2018. Thereafter, updates are made four times a year during the whole duration of One Health EJP. In the first year of One Health EJP, the Stakeholders contact list focuses on the Key EU stakeholders (collaboration with WP1 and WP2). The full Stakeholders contact list will be ready by the time when outcomes from the Joint research projects and Joint integrative projects are expected (collaboration with WP3 and WP4). In the final Year 5 of

the One Health EJP, the Stakeholders contact list will place more focus on sustainability (collaboration with WP7).

The Stakeholders contact list includes contact details of the contact persons. The data collected for the Stakeholders contact list is the minimal data needed for the purpose of keeping the contact: name, email, organisation. This list will be available to the One Health consortium in the password-protected part of the One Health EJP website. WP5 uses the contact list for dialogue with the stakeholders, including tailored dissemination of output of the One Health EJP. All in the One Health EJP consortium are also encouraged to be in direct contact with the stakeholders – in particular with the regional and national stakeholders. The interactions should be informed to WP5 for follow-up and reporting.

3.2. Stakeholders contact list, February 2018

3.2.1. Stakeholders identified, February 2018

The stakeholders identified at the start of One Health EJP are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Stakeholders identified at the start of One Health EJP.

	Key EU stakeholders	Other EU stakeholders	Key global stakeholders	Other global stakeholders	Key national stakeholders	Other regional and national stakeholders
Pre-identified	ECDC	Directorate-General Agriculture and Rural Development, European Commission	WHO		Programme owners	
	EFSA	Department 'Industrial Leadership and Societal Challenges', Research Executive Agency, European Commission	OIE		Other ministries of the countries within the consortium	
	Directorate-General Health and Food Safety, European Commission		FAO		Mirror groups	
Identified after January 1st 2018		EMA				Ministries in other countries
		EDA				
		EEA				
Stakeholders Committee members at the start of One Health EJP	ECDC, EFSA					

Key EU stakeholders

The two Key EU stakeholders for dialogue during One Health EJP are the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). Directorate-General Health and Food Safety, European Commission, is also identified as Key EU stakeholder, with which WP5 will have close communication.

Other EU stakeholders

Other EU stakeholders pre-identified were Directorate-General Agriculture and Rural Development, and Department 'Industrial Leadership and Societal Challenges', Research Executive Agency of European Commission. More EU stakeholders are being identified during the activities of WP5, in particular from the activities related to identifying research and integrative needs of the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA. The first example is EMA, which was identified from the document search and knowledge on the close collaboration on issues related to antimicrobial resistance and antimicrobial use. EDA and EEA were identified from PMT meeting minutes (September 09, 2017, Paris).

Key global stakeholders

Pre-identified international stakeholders are WHO, OIE, and FAO.

Other global stakeholders

More global stakeholders might be identified during the activities of WP5.

Key national stakeholders

The pre-identified Key national stakeholders are programme owners, other ministries of the countries within the consortium, and mirror groups.

Other regional and national stakeholders

Ministries of other countries, in particular of other EU member states, are relevant stakeholders for the future.

3.2.2. The first Stakeholders contact list

The first Stakeholders contact list is compiled by the end of February 2018. This list focuses on the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA and includes the contact persons for the first dialogue needed at the start of the One Health EJP.

4. Communication procedure with stakeholders

Communication procedure aims to ensure efficient receiving of the research and integrative needs of the stakeholders by One Health EJP, tailored dissemination of results of One Health EJP to the stakeholders, and timely alignment of One Health EJP activities with other activities. The communication takes place all the time during the One Health EJP. WP5 reports to Stakeholders Committee annually.

4.1. Process to establish the Communication procedure

Communication links are established and maintained in close collaboration with WP1 and WP2. The Communication procedure is applying these links for correspondence, participation in specific meetings, and discussion of the Dissemination strategy of WP5.

Communication with the pre-identified Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA started by invitation to Stakeholders Committee and by presentations and discussions at KOM. Directorate-General Health and Food Safety, European Commission, gave a Keynote Address at KOM.

Dialogue about research and integrative needs is the first priority in the communication at the early phase of One Health EJP, so that the first identified research and integrative needs can be provided for consideration for inclusion in the Strategic Research Agenda (WP2), which will be the basis for the second call for Joint Research projects (WP3) and Joint Integrative projects (WP4). The focus in this communication are the two Key EU stakeholders and this communication includes the first Stakeholders contact list.

The first Stakeholders contact list is compiled using the Structure analysis approach on ECDC and EFSA. The first Key contacts of ECDC and EFSA are consulted during the preparation of the first Stakeholders contact list. The first Stakeholders contact list is then contacted by email to the dialogue about research and integrative needs, which will be provided for consideration for inclusion in the Strategic Research Agenda (WP2). Moreover, the contacts are asked for possible ways of collaboration. The answers will shape the Communication procedure. Formats of targeted

communication will be developed and implemented, and discussion about the Dissemination strategy of WP5 is started early.

The Communication procedure is later expanded to the wider future versions of the Stakeholders contact list. As soon as the website of One Health EJP is up, it will serve as the main technical platform and forum for interaction with stakeholders. In collaboration with WP1, specific tools for communication with the stakeholders will be implemented, e.g. restricted areas on the website or within a virtual research environment.

4.2. Communication procedure established with stakeholders, February 2018

The Key communication links are established. The first Key contacts are Piotr Kramarz, ECDC, and Marta Hugas, EFSA, who are in the Stakeholders Committee and attended KOM. The contact at Directorate-General Health and Food Safety, European Commission, is Kris de Smet.

The first Stakeholders contact list is compiled by the end of February 2018, and all on the list will be contacted by in March 2018. The first communication will be by emails and focuses on the dialogue on the first identified research and integrative needs, which will be provided for consideration for inclusion in the Strategic Research Agenda.

5. List of abbreviations

BfR	Federal Institute for Risk Assessment
EC	European Commission
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EDA	European Defence Agency
EEA	European Environment Agency
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EJP	European Joint Programme
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
M2	Month 2, second month of One Health EJP: February 2018
OIE	World Organisation for Animal Health
PMT	The Project Management Team
SSI	Statens Serum Institut
WP	Work Package
WHO	World Health Organization